

Antonello Ricci e Mimmo Morello, *Suono di famiglia. Memoria e musica in un paese della Calabria greca-nica*, Udine, Nota, pp. 120, con CD e DVD, 2018. ISBN 978-88-941462-2-6.

Domenico Di Virgilio, Filippo Bonini Baraldi e Gianfranco Spitilli, *Giannina Malaspina cantastorie*, Teramo, Associazione Culturale Banbun – Edizioni Centro Studi Don Nicola Jobbi, pp. 256, con CD, 2017. ISBN 978-88-941462-2-6.

The two volumes *Suono di famiglia. Memoria e musica in un paese della Calabria greca-nica* and *Giannina Malaspina cantastorie* apparently seem to tell different stories. The former is devoted to a music for dance and celebrations that is part of the musical traditions of Palizzi (RC), Calabria, South Italy. The latter tells us about a specific repertoire from Central Italy (specifically Abruzzo and the neighbouring regions), namely that of the storytellers of religious songs, in particular the *diasillari*, who used to sing for the deceased.

Despite the inner and geographical distance between these repertoires, well-illustrated by the accompanying CDs, the two books have several elements in common which convinced me to write a single review. First of all, both the authors carried out their fieldwork in a similar way and produced their writings with a similar philosophy. These books are an excellent demonstration of how Italian Ethnomusicology can carry on the classic fieldwork of its origins, about Italian folklore, with refined up-to-date research methodology and restitution.

In both cases the point of departure is not the music in itself but the musicians. Their life stories, their genealogies, and the places they lived in or visited. Everything is synchronically and diachronically part of a unique musical process. Every detail is part of a bigger framework of cultural knowledge and practice. Music is seen as culture, produced by specific persons in specific situations and needs a reflexive, dialogic and participatory attitude by the ethnographer (Barz, Cooley 2008: 16-17). In the words of Antonello Ricci: «Questo lavoro è incentrato sui saperi musicali, sulla trasmissione della memoria dei suoni, sulla costruzione dell'identità personale e familiare mediante l'espressività sonora, sulla dimensione sociale del fare musica, sulle dinamiche culturali che oggi orientano la pratica della musica nella Calabria aspromontana» (: 7).¹ In *Giannina Malaspina*, the lived experience of Giannina and her family is crucial to understanding her status of musician and the role of *diasillari* in Central Italian folk society.

¹ This work is focused on the musical knowledge, on the transmission of sound memory, on the construction of personal and family identity through sonic expressivity, on the social dimension of music making, on cultural dynamics that today guide the musical practice in Calabria of Aspromonte.

Part of this framework is also the relationship between the researchers and the musicians. We can define both these works as dialogic (Feld 1987). Antonello Ricci shares the authoriality with Mimmo Morello, the musician at the centre of the book. After a short but deep introduction, Ricci leaves space for Morello's narration. This is undoubtedly influenced by the conversations they had during the years of fieldwork Ricci did in Calabria, but nevertheless allows for a subjective and autobiographical style.

«La storia inizia così»² starts Mimmo Morello, who then goes through his musical life, telling the reader when he first encountered all the instruments he plays, why he decided to learn them and when, where and why he played them for the first time. In so doing he offers to the reader a family network, a world of social relations, and nets of knowledge that are widespread over the territory around his birthplace: Palizzi. A third part is even more autobiographical: a simple transcript of some crucial conversations Mimmo Morello had with his grandfather Lello Siviglia and his grandmother Anna Ligato and with Carmelo Battaglia and Caterina Siviglia who are linked to Mimmo through a kind of real and/or musical kinship. These conversations enhance the framework already portrayed by Mimmo Morello.

«La musica è una cosa seria»³ says his grandfather, as he describes the social role of music, the passion musicians must have and must show in their performance, the occasions for music, always through personal stories. These transcripts are also precious because they add value and information to the content, thanks to the language and the specific words chosen to talk about music (Merriam 1964).

This slice of life is reinforced through several media: a copious collection of family photographs, a rich CD with sound recordings and a DVD with 4 videos. 80 pictures from the 1950s to 2013 show us the musicians' genealogy, but also reflect on the research that produced this book, giving us frames of the meetings between Antonello Ricci and Mimmo Morello and his family, documenting their body language and attitude. A rich illustration of the transmission of musical techniques and body postures from one generation to another. The photos do not need to have perfect focus, but they have to show a specific moment, with its movements and emotions. The DVD contains three amateur home videos⁴ which give faces, motion, setting to the musical life learnt through the book. A precious testimony, from the direct protagonists of that world, that allows us to participate in the real ritual events held in Palizzi. We can understand how music is crucial to these events.

More added value is given by the fourth video, a documentary created from the shootings Nino Cannatà, an insider filmmaker, made between 2009 and 2013 during the fieldwork related to the book. We can define this video as mostly a restitution of re-

² «This is how it all starts».

³ «Music is a serious thing».

⁴ A National Archive of Home Movies, the Home Movies Association has been set up in Italy. See Edmonds, Simoni, Fiorini (2007) and Cati (2009).

search video-recordings that are intentionally unrefined in terms of editing, because the selection Cannatà made is already a sort of non-chronological narration through images that constantly relate to things one encounters both in the book and on the CD. This connection is well evident in the notes to the CD, because they indicate, piece by piece, the video and the pictures connected to each piece.

Una complessa organizzazione multimediale che mette in relazione dati, immagini, rappresentazioni di forme espressive della voce e di tecniche e pratiche del corpo a dare una reale consistenza all'idea, che ha dato luogo a questo lavoro, della concreta esistenza di uno stile musicale di famiglia (: 70).⁵

The CD offers an extraordinary number of musical examples: 49 pieces recorded mostly during 2011 by Antonello Ricci in Palizzi with an excellent recording quality. *Tarantelle, muttetta, balli, sonate*, but also *filastrocche* for learning to play the accordion (track 8) and many proverbs (tracks 14-29) recited by Leo Siviglia, Mimmo's uncle. It shows the wide repertoire and the high musical quality of Mimmo Morello and his family, their instrumental techniques and the particularly intense quality of their voices. We can discover the "family style" explained in the book, which goes from lyrical songs to a complex repertoire of music for dance: from *pizzicarello* to valzer. Track 33A is a special fragment that I really appreciated for its rarity, since it is an example of a single reed repertoire.

The CD also offers an important message. In presenting nursery rhymes and several proverbs, it shows how in a repertoire "music" cannot be separated from "narration" or "enunciation". We can listen to how every vocal expression has its sonic rules, which progressively gain distance from the everyday spoken voice. Every utterance has specific melodic and rhythmic elements that strengthen it. And there is continuity between all these forms in this, just as there is in many other repertoires that cannot be ignored (Giannattasio 2005).

What the authors want to demonstrate is "family imprinting", how it is transmitted and how it is performed. We can see the role played by bodily experience and emotions in the learning process, memorization, technique and performance improvement.

Here we find an explanation for those local and family styles that emerged from the early classifications made by the first ethnomusicological fieldwork carried out in Italy. Such an explanation comes from the inside, as a product of a family prototype, the generative nucleus of a specific idea of sound. A sound made up of multiple elements: melody, vertical relations between parts, specific timbres for voices and instruments. Everything produces unique and peculiar sonic forms.

⁵ A complex multimodal organisation that relates data, images, representation of expressive forms of voice and body practices, to give consistency to the idea, at the basis of this work, of a concrete existence of a musical family style.

«Shifting the emphasis away from representation (text) toward experience», to use the words of Barz and Cooley (2008: 4), the authors of *Giannina Malaspina* introduce us to their book by saying «Ciò che ci sta veramente a cuore è che il lettore possa conoscere la storia di Giannina e Marino attraverso tre “finestre” temporali distinte, corrispondenti ai periodi in cui ciascuno di noi ha frequentato Marino, Giannina, Francesco e le loro famiglie, dai primi anni Novanta fino ad oggi» (: 9).⁶

Here too, then, the book is centred on the life stories of Giannina and her family, in particular her husband, Marino, and her nephew Francesco, which emerged from the meetings they had with the authors. This time the autobiographical cipher is doubled: on the one hand, there is the content, Giannina's real life, while, on the other, we have the authors' writing style, as they reconstruct the musical life of Giannina and Marino through the personal experiences they had together. In this case too, family ties and stories are also shown through a large amount of pictures.

Domenico Di Virgilio starts positioning himself in this framework as a witness of the culture of *cantastorie* in the religious life of the Abruzzi which he reconstructs with literature, archival testimonies and direct interactions with Giannina and her entourage.

Gianfranco Spitilli contextualizes his contribution starting from the life of Giannina's father, Tiberio Malaspina. Just like Antonello Ricci, he is aware of the importance of family lives and ties in musical life. In his interpretation, Giannina's infancy, marked by mourning, played a strong role in the fact that she became a *diasillara*, a singer of death, and a *santese*, singer of the saints.

Una funzione cerimoniale itinerante del tutto rivolta allo spazio geografico ed emblematico del margine, della periferia abitata al limite estremo di demarcazione fra il domestico e il selvatico [...]: una dimensione privilegiata d'interazione vivi-morti messa in atto attraverso una forma di mendicizia ritualmente connotata che ha assimilato nel corso dei secoli ambulanti e questuanti all'universo dei defunti e delle anime vaganti, ancora diffusamente avvertibile nell'ideologia religiosa dell'Europa rurale della seconda metà del Novecento (: 50-51).⁷

Spitilli contextualizes the musical life of Giannina and her husband Mario within a larger framework, mixing their testimonies with the existing documentation and bibliography about similar (or the same) repertoires, mostly as observed by Peter Burke (1980) and Carlo Ginzburg (1998). The cipher of his writing is the exaltation of the

⁶ What matters to us most is that the reader can know Giannina and Marino through three distinct time windows, which correspond to the periods each of us hung out with Marino, Giannina, Francesco and their families, from the 1990s till today.

⁷ «An itinerant ceremonial function totally devoted to the geographical and emblematic space of the margin, of the inhabited periphery at the extreme limit of demarcation between domestic and wild [...]: a privileged dimension of the interaction between life and death enacted through a ritually connoted form of begging that over the centuries equated peddlers and beggars to the world of the dead and of the wandering souls, still strongly present in the religious ideology of rural Europe in the second half of the XXth century».

liminality of their existence, of the role of their repertoire and its consistency. Giannina and her husband's repertoire consisted in a genuine *multi-media* system between orality and manuscripts or printed texts, a point of encounter between strictly codified religious traditions and the genres of ballad and rhymed historical narrations, widespread all over Central and South Italy (Leydi 1978).

The focus of the authors is their experience with Giannina, which is why the title of the book is only addressed to Giannina. Her husband passed away and could not take part in the recent projects.

Filippo Bonini Baraldi's contribution is more autobiographical. His aim is to talk about, and reflect on the project merging musical creation and ethnomusicological fieldwork (Pettan 2015) that he and a group of musicians realized with Giannina and her nephew. Bonini Baraldi reconstructs the positioning of every participant, with his/her background of life and musical experience and gives a detailed account of what happened, from the first encounter with Giannina in 2006 to the recordings of 2016. He tells how his group went from Paris to Arsita (TE) and then took Giannina and her nephew Francesco to Paris and Lisbon. «Ciò che qui conta sono gli incroci che si sono creati nel tempo, il groviglio e intrico di molteplici segmenti di vita» (: 90).⁸ This allows him to paint a broader picture of the encounter between musicians from different cultures, from reproduction-conservation, to ethno-avant-garde to world music. In his opinion what they realized was something different, beyond the simple dichotomies of centre/periphery, insider-outsider.

The musical encounter was made just by playing. «Cercavamo delle traiettorie delle voci e degli strumenti più aperte possibile, per coordinarci rapidamente con una proposta proveniente da un altro musicista, senza strategie preesistenti ed evitando di organizzare gli strumenti in strati gerarchici» (: 96).⁹ In so doing it was not an encounter between Giannina and the others: no one is at the centre of the net, but everyone is part of it and has the same weight. They realized a «mobilità rizomatica slegata da interessi economici, che possa solidificare dei legami, rafforzare delle relazioni umane, piuttosto che consumarle».¹⁰

Filippo Bonini Baraldi's narration introduces a second element that is common to both books, albeit strongly explicit in *Giannina Malaspina cantastorie* and less pronounced in *Suono di famiglia*. In depicting their family and fieldwork experiences what emerges is the "root-ness" (Clifford 1997). The focus of Morello and Ricci's book is Mimmo Morello's family musical genealogy and his specific musical experience, but it also shows how musicians are both rooted in a specific place and style, and at the same

⁸ The intersections created in time, the tangles and knots of several life segments are important here.

⁹ «We were trying as far as possible to find open trajectories for both voices and instruments, quickly coordinating with the rousing proposals from different musicians, without any pre-existent strategy and avoiding organizing instruments in hierarchical strata».

¹⁰ «Rhizomatic mobility unrelated to profit, able to solidify connections, to reinforce human relations, rather than consuming them».

time move from place to place, from musician to musician. Spitilli designs a “geographical genealogy” of Giannina’s father’s and mother’s origins, underlining the itinerant nature of the singer and her family.

Nell’ambito rurale di allora si muovevano, a vario titolo, figure che noi oggi chiameremmo “on the road” [...] Alcune di queste figure, diasillari, santarellari, nomadi di varie etnie, gli stessi zampognari, avevano fatto di necessità cultura; e con i loro transiti e Novene di Natale scandivano di questa realtà il tempo circolare (: 29).¹¹

A third strong affinity between these books is the relevance of the body, emotions and corporeal experience in music making. These «pratiche del corpo e della voce»,¹² well described in Morello – Ricci, are strongly present in *Giannina Malaspina Cantastorie*. One of the first things all the authors underline is Giannina’s vocal quality. Di Virgilio states that she had «quella voce che solo le donne che sono state contadine sapevano e sanno tirar fuori; una voce stridente, acuta, estremamente significativa del loro modo di essere: lo specchio della loro esistenza» (: 27).¹³ Spitilli describes Giannina’s singing as «un grido di dolore, liberatorio e vincolante al contempo. Uno sforzo inaudito [...] La sua voce improvvisa satura lo spazio acustico [...] Tutto il suo volto si trasfigura in una smorfia sofferta, i muscoli del collo si tendono e si increspano» (: 49).¹⁴ Bonini Baraldi starts his description of his first meeting with Giannina by saying: «La prima volta che sentii Giannina cantare fu un vero colpo di fulmine. La sua voce, spinta fino al limite della resistenza fisica, fa venire le lacrime agli occhi anche a chi non ha familiarità con questo tipo di repertorio» (: 81).¹⁵

Giannina’s voice bursts through the CD recordings and is evoked in the vocal choices made by the other musicians. The CD is the sonic demonstration in both voices and instruments of the convergence between two different musical worlds: that of Giannina and Mario and that of Filippo Bonini Baraldi and his musicians. It presents 9 tracks of extremely good quality: 3 songs from the Giannina Malaspina and Marino Ciprietti repertoire: *Dijesilla*, *Il miracolo di Santa Rita*, *l’Orazione di Sant’Antonio* (tracks 1, 5 and 7, all recorded in 1993 at Macchie di Farindola by Domenico Di Virgilio) and 6 different elaborations of these songs in performances that took place at different times

¹¹ «The rural world of that period was inhabited by various figures we would now call “on the road”. [...] Some of these figures, such as *diasillari* [singers for the dead], *santarellari* [singers for saints], nomads from various ethnic groups, even *zampognari* [bagpipe players] were forced by circumstances to enhance their own culture; and their to-ing and fro-ing and Christmas Novenas marked the circular time of the existence».

¹² «Bodily and vocal practices».

¹³ «That voice that only a woman who has been a peasant could and can show; a shrill, high voice that strongly expresses their way of being: the mirror of their existence».

¹⁴ «A scream of pain, liberating and constraining at the same time. An inconceivable effort [...]. Her sudden voice fills the sonic space [...] Her whole face is transfigured by a suffering grimace, the muscles in her neck stretched taut».

¹⁵ «The first time I heard Giannina singing it was love at first sight. Her voice, pushed to the limit of her physical possibilities, brings tears to the eyes of anyone who is not familiar with this repertoire».

and in different places: Guazzano di Campli in 2014 (tr. 2, 4, 6, 8 and 9), Lisbon 2016 (tr. 3). The distribution of the tracks shows the entanglement that came about between these musicians and their way of interpreting this repertoire. Notes to the various pieces are essential, while transcriptions and the complete texts are presented only for the recordings of 1993. This is because they are a final part of a path that runs through the entire text. Every contribution adds its own piece to the entire picture. Di Virgilio shows the quality of Giannina's voice with several spectrograms, Spitilli contextualizes the repertoire, Bonini Baraldi gives the interpretive keys to understanding the recordings of 2014 and 2016.

This is a unique and effective way to offer possible life to folk tradition nowadays.

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